

Optimized Collective Algorithm with MPI Sub-Group Creation based on Topology Mapping from a statistical Tree-Model Data Classifier

Chandan Basu^{*}, Johan Raber

National Supercomputer Center, Linköping University, SE-581 83 Linköping

Abstract

A network topology aware MPI all-to-all algorithm which was developed in earlier PRACE project is improved. The interface of the all-to-all routine is made similar to MPI all-to-all routine. The routine is being tested for accuracy.

A new data classifier routine is developed to collect network characteristics data. The classifier works very well and in a scalable way when categories are as well separated in feature space. A new data collection scheme is developed. The scalability of the data acquisition has been partly addressed but there are remaining issues to be solved.

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern clusters have a hierarchy of network bandwidth and latency between pairs of ranks. We try to detect this network hierarchy and use this information to implement optimized MPI collective operations. We present in this white paper an ongoing activity aimed at improving the MPI performance by making MPI collective communications topology aware. The development began in the PRACE-1IP work package 7 and is continuing in PRACE-2IP work package 12.

Our work can be broadly divided into two related lines. One line is the algorithm based approach to improve collective communications. In this approach we take some static information about the cluster, e.g., number of cores per node etc. and use that information together with actual rank placements on nodes in our optimized collective algorithms. Earlier, we have reported [1] an efficient implementation of `MPI_Alltoallv` and shown performance improvement on PRACE synthetic benchmark code `mod2f` [2]. In this whitepaper we report further improvements of our implementation of all-to-all routine called `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned`. We have mostly tried to improve the interface of our implementation so that it can be easily used in an application program by replacing standard `MPI_Alltoallv` without the need of code modification.

The other line followed by us is to improve our method of topology detection using a statistical tree-model data classifier. This will give us more fine grained information about the network at run time, e.g., placement of ranks within same numa zone, ranks within same CPU socket, ranks within same node, ranks within same switch etc. In our current implementation we are collecting relevant data and doing the analysis off-line.

The optimization and automatic sub-group creation of MPI collectives in the present study relies on a statistical categorization of rank-to-rank communication data samples, where differences in e.g. bandwidth and latencies are recorded. The size of data sample used in a particular experiment is same for all rank pairs. The recorded data samples are then assigned a category used for the automatic MPI sub-group creation and rank assignment depending on their measured member values. We have in a previous study [3] applied an unsupervised classifier to such records, the k-means data clustering technique [4], to a moderate degree of success. However, that study revealed weaknesses in the approach with respect to the data collection technique used as well as the quality of results obtained by the unsupervised classifier and raised questions regarding its scalability beyond a couple of hundred ranks.

There have been several other studies on the subject of automatic interconnect topology detection [5], [6], [7], [8]. The methods developed in these studies have often relied on tools tracing interconnect traffic and querying interconnect equipment, making

^{*} Corresponding author: cbasu@nsc.liu.se

them somewhat less portable, in one case requiring super user privileges to boot and furthermore restricting the method’s employment to InfiniBand interconnects. However, the latter study cited successfully made use of statistical methods for interconnect topology determination – the Neighbor-Joining [9] technique, a method closely related to hierarchical clustering [10] – in a reasonably scalable way. As encouraging as this was for the statistical approach also taken in this study, the method was still restricted to InfiniBand networks and was not fully distributed in its implementation.

With respect to interconnect topology detection, it is the aim in the present study to develop an *interconnect technology agnostic*, fully distributed method to facilitate the automatic creation of MPI sub-groups at runtime. In fact, since the MPI sub-groups creation is only a means to utilize available interconnect features such as bandwidth and latency in a more optimized way than the standard implementation, the actual topology is not the primary concern to determine, rather it is the detection and categorization of interconnect “performance tiers” which is the primary concern. Naturally, this should also for the vast majority of cases reflect the underlying interconnect topology.

Where we previously used the k-means method for classification of point-to-point communications we will now instead turn to a different type of statistical classifier, the binary regression tree type outlined in section 2.2.3. We have also worked on the shortcomings of our previous data collection implementation, primarily to get deterministic coverage in the data record sampling procedure and achieve higher scalability by fully parallelizing the data acquisition implementation.

2 DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES

2.1 Topology-aware all-to-all communication

2.1.1 Description

The optimized `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned` that was developed earlier [1] does the same operation as `MPI_Alltoallv` but it utilizes the intra node bandwidth more efficiently. It distinguishes between ranks in the same node and ranks across different nodes and streamlines the communications accordingly. We have already shown [1] that it leads to performance improvements. However the interface of `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned` was not same as the standard `MPI_Alltoallv`. To use `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned` changes are required in the application code which is not easy to achieve in complex legacy codes. In PRACE-2IP work package 12 we are working on improving the interface of `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned` to make it same as `MPI_Alltoallv`. In our recent white-paper [3] we have described in detail our new approach. We have now implemented a new optimized all-to-all routine called `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new` which has the same interface as the `MPI_Alltoallv`.

The interface of our earlier implementation called `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned` was:

```
int MPI_Alltoallv_tuned (double *bufin, ptarr gr_scnt, ptarr gr_sdpl, double *bufout,
ptarr gr_rcnt, ptarr gr_rdpl, gcom new_comm);
```

Where `ptarr` and `gcom` have the following data types:

```
typedef struct {int *intra; int *inter;} ptarr;
typedef struct {MPI_Comm intra_comm; MPI_Comm inter_comm;} gcom;
```

The `gcom` data type has two components `intra_comm` and `inter_comm`. The `intra_comm` is the communicator within node. The `inter_comm` is the communicator across nodes. Each process in `inter_comm` has same rank from `intra_comm` and vice-versa. The intra component of the `ptarr` contains the information relevant to intra node communication. The inter component of `ptarr` contains information related to inter node communication. As an example the `gr_scnt.intra` is an array containing send counts within the node whereas `gr_scnt.inter` is an array containing send counts across nodes. The size of the `gcom` structure is twice that of `MPI_Comm`. The size of `ptarr` is twice the size of an integer array of size `np`, where `np` is the number of ranks. The extra memory consumption due to these new structures are marginal. The corresponding standard `MPI_Alltoallv` has the following interface:

```
int MPI_Alltoallv (void *bufin, int *scnt, int *sdpl, MPI_Datatype stype,
void *bufout, int *rcnt, int *rdpl, MPI_Datatype rtype, MPI_Comm comm)
```

In our earlier implementation before calling `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned` one needs to call some initialization routine which calculates `gr_scnt`, `gr_sdpl`, `gr_rcnt`, `gr_rdpl`, `new_comm` from `scnt`, `sdpl`, `rcnt`, `rdpl` and `comm` respectively. This routine has some overhead as it involves MPI communications inside. In many typical use cases where `MPI_Alltoallv` is called repeatedly only `bufin` and `bufout` changes between successive calls. So it is sufficient to call the initialization routine only once and thereby reducing the initialization overhead to negligible.

In our new implementation called `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new` the interface is:

```
int MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new(void *bufin, int *scnt, int *sdpl, MPI_Datatype stype,
void *bufout, int *rcnt, int *rdpl, MPI_Datatype rtype, MPI_Comm comm)
```

which is same as the standard `MPI_Alltoallv` interface. We have moved the initialization routine inside `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new`. However inside `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new` initialization is done only once for a particular “*communication type*”. A “*communication type*” means same value of `scnt`, `sdpl`, `rcnt`, `rdpl` and `comm`. We identify each “*communication type*” by a unique key value calculated by Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) algorithm [3]. For a new key value which corresponds to new “*communication type*” the initialization routine is called. Once the initialization is done the key value and the corresponding `gr_scnt`, `gr_sdpl`, `gr_rcnt`, `gr_rdpl`, `new_comm` values are stored in an internal database. For another call to `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new` with same “*communication type*” the key matches with the old key value stored in the database. Hence the initialization routine is not called but corresponding `gr_scnt`, `gr_sdpl`, `gr_rcnt`, `gr_rdpl`, `new_comm` values are retrieved from the database. This makes the overhead negligible. The `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new` can be used on `MPI_COMM_WORLD` or any other derived communicator.

2.1.2 Results

We have now finished our implementation. We are doing functionality tests of the routine for correctness. We are doing tests for different input data types, different sizes of communicators etc. The routine works for most test cases. There are some corner cases, e.g., if original rank distribution is non uniform across nodes then our current implementation fails. Non uniform rank distribution can occur if the application requests odd number of ranks from the scheduler in a homogeneous cluster or if the cluster itself is heterogeneous. These cases are generally rare. We are still working to fix this problem.

2.2 Automatic network topology identification

2.2.1 Data clustering methods

Any interconnected system of compute units, or nodes, will exhibit performance tiers in terms of MPI message transfer times between MPI ranks. These access times can be recorded for a range of message sizes, thereby forming the basis to a classification of these tiers into categories. These categories should in almost all cases reflect the underlying network topology, for instance intra-node communications, cc-NUMA intra-node communications and inter-node communications. Depending on the interconnect topology used and the accuracy of the measurements it is also conceivable that tiers in the interconnect fabric can be detected mapping to, for instance, how many interconnect switches there are between communicating ranks.

The problems we address in the automatic topology detection part of this study are the scalability of the data acquisition phase and the subsequent classification of the data thus recorded into a category to be used for automatic MPI sub-group creation.

Summarizing the algorithm we aim to implement:

Before runtime:

1. Collect a data records training set of representative features with mapping to performance categories.
2. From this data, make a *classification key* to use at runtime

At runtime:

1. At MPI initialization, collect MPI communication data records
2. For all rank pairs, apply the *classification key* to assign a performance tier category to the rank pair
3. From this category, assign the ranks to their target MPI sub-group

The main difference to our previous work lies in shifting track with respect to the statistical classifier, going from a completely unsupervised classifier requiring $O(n^2)$ number of comparisons at runtime to one requiring $O(n)$ with a pre-requisite training step.

2.2.2 Data Records Acquisition

The previous data records collector implemented by us sampled rank pair data in a stochastic way using a uniform distribution when selecting pairs for each sampling round and needed quite long runtimes to reach full coverage of all rank pairs. This proved to not scale beyond a couple of hundred ranks, not really usable if we aim for high scalability, so we designed a new implementation.

The number of unique rank pairs (disregarding pair order) for a set of N MPI ranks is $N(N-1)/2$. For an appropriate algorithm the number of unique rank pairs that can be sampled at any time is asymptotically approaching $N/2$ as N increases, making the number of data sampling iterations to cover all rank pairs approaching $N-1$. That is, ideally there should be linear scaling with respect to the number of MPI ranks for the data sampling phase, given that an appropriate algorithm is devised and implemented.

The crux here is to at each iteration of data sampling create $N/2$ unique rank pairs to set up communications between and in subsequent data sampling iterations avoid pair repeats of previous iterations. This can be accomplished (and trivially implemented) using the observation that in a cyclic list, elements spanning 0 to N , pairs formed symmetrically around a position in the cyclic list will be unique and will not be repeated as the symmetry position is moved in the list. Additionally, it has to be realized that there are two ways to lay out symmetry around such a position, one with an even number of list elements between any given pair, and one with an odd number of list elements between pairs.

Using this observation, we made a function taking as arguments an MPI rank number, the total number of MPI ranks and the data sampling iteration number, which returned the corresponding MPI rank to pair with. Provided that the time for each data sampling round is not increasing with the total number of MPI ranks, we should have linear scaling data acquisition time with the size of the job.

2.2.3 Classification and Regression Trees (CART)

The CART model [11] is a very simple model for making predictions and classifications based on recursive binary subdivision of data “feature space” until a unique prediction or classification can be made. In the CART model, a prediction represents a real number estimate as the response of data input, whereas a classification is a category outcome, or in other words the discrete version of a prediction.

To make predictions or classifications, training data must be used to generate a *classification key*, a set of tests, binary splits, to apply on any new data sample which will result in a unique classification.

In the present case we could have a data feature space consisting of data like bandwidth, latencies, message rates and derived data from these such as their respective standard deviations if many samplings are made. The samplings could furthermore be done using a range of message sizes. This could make the feature space arbitrarily complex and it is of course desirable to make feature space as compact as possible while still allowing accurate classifications. In our previous investigation, we found bandwidth data for 1MiB message size alone would be sufficient for classification, in that case, by mere inspection of a data scatter plot. For this reason, using solely bandwidth data is the approach we have followed here.

The chief virtues of the CART model in the current context are its inherent simplicity and trivial implementation in the classification phase. The more arduous task of creating the classification key is well implemented in the statistical programming environment R [12] and can be simply obtained by a script and transferred to a configuration file to be read runtime. Also, applying the classification key to a sample data record is a negligible computational effort as it will, for any trial classification category tested against, consist of only a small number of comparison operations. Since all data records are independent of each other, this is also an embarrassingly parallel problem for a data set. This can then be done on the fly on a per-rank basis as data samples are recorded.

2.2.4 Results and Discussion

We are in the very early stages of obtaining and analyzing results, making it impossible to draw firm conclusions about our implementation of the data acquisition and classification. We will present results about the data classifier accuracy and the scaling of the runtime data acquisition.

Our previous data acquisition method yielded data of remarkably well separated bandwidth tiers, see figure 1, which led us to focus on this as the primary basis of classification. However, redoing this data collection using the new data acquisition scheme gave a very surprising, and to us puzzling, result. Where we previously had very well defined peaks, there is now a very evident smear of the data peaks. The cause of this smearing is as yet unknown to us. If it is not a bug in our implementation, the most significant change in our data collection routine is making it more effective, very close to full network activity, where previously we were less effective.

Figure 1: Kernel density plots from bandwidth data collected from 256 ranks using our previous data collection method (left) and our present implementation (right). The bandwidth is in bits/s and the total density is normalized to one in both cases.

With respect to making a classification key, this smeared data cannot possibly make a good basis for classification. In fact, this data is full of records which would be incorrectly classified, evident by even a cursory glance at it. We need to continue to investigate the root cause of this smearing to make the current data acquisition method a viable choice here.

If we use data from our previous data collection (left in figure 1) to generate a classification key we obtain very good results, as to be expected on such well separated data, with no misclassifications of the 32640 unique rank pairs, using the key depicted in figure 2.

Figure 2: Classification key generated from previous data collector on 256 ranks, 32640 unique rank pairs. There are no misclassifications using this simple key. Category “c1” denotes intra-NUMA zone point-to-point communications. Category “c2” denotes intra-node, inter-NUMA zone communications. Category “c3” denotes inter-node communications.

The implementation of the key of figure 2. in C would be:

```

if ( bandwidth < 737776587.952 ) {
    category = c3;
} else if ( bandwidth < 2050481983.979 ) {
    category = c2;
} else {
    category = c1;
}
  
```

This illustrates the chief virtue of the CART model in the runtime classification case, i.e. the simplicity of implementation and hints at the scalability inherent to this approach to classification.

The scalability of the data acquisition phase is another matter. As indicated above, provided that data acquisition round timings stay the same over the course of collection, there should be linear scaling of the data collection time as the total number of ranks increases. This seems to be true up-to few hundred ranks. For instance, running on 64 ranks takes 12 seconds and running on 1024 ranks takes 238 seconds. The time increase is roughly proportional to the increase in ranks.

Data collection time vs no. of ranks

Figure 3: The data collection time

But as we scale up the time increase is no longer linear. For instance, running on 4096 ranks takes 1428 seconds. Compared to 64 rank run time it is super-linear increase of runtime. This can be also seen in the Figure 3. The root cause for this is not yet investigated. What is clear is that the rank pair generation scheme is not the root cause as this is very fast and scaling linearly when done in a distributed way. This leaves the OS kernel, IB driver and MPI libraries or some aspect of our implementation left to investigate.

The conclusion of the results obtained this far is that the classifier works very well and in a scalable way when categories are as well separated in feature space as obtained with our previous data collection implementation. The scalability of the data acquisition has been partly addressed but there are remaining issues to be solved. Alternative approaches to the data collection method may need to be employed. Furthermore, the accuracy of the data collected must be at the same level as that of our previous data collection scheme for the classification to work which will require the root cause of the data “smearing” to be found.

3 FURTHER WORK

We will continue to work to make `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new` more robust. The few corner cases where the current routine fails, e.g., non uniform rank distribution across nodes are unlikely to occur in most resource allocations. However we have to take care of these cases for completeness sake. We also want to test it on real applications by replacing call to `MPI_Alltoallv` by `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned_new`. We are planning to continue this work in PRACE-2IP work package 12 extension phase. In this phase we will take some well known application code which is heavily dependent on All-to-all operation and try our All-to-all routine for performance improvements.

With respect to automated topology detection, future work will be directed towards finding the root causes of the scalability issues and data measurement quality issues of the present implementation. We will also work on improving the scalability and accuracy of the data collection algorithm by building a linked list data structure of relationships between nodes which would allow fewer rank pairs to be sampled. There is also a possibility to choose selectively which ranks should be part of this list by restricting the set to contain only one rank per compute node. Intra-node classification would then be done separately.

We aim to investigate whether including other data than bandwidth into the classifier as the computational cost runtime is negligible and could allow tiers on the interconnect level to be detected.

Usability and flexibility should be improved by the introduction of a configuration file to be read at runtime for the classification key.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was financially supported by the PRACE-2IP project funded in part by the EUs 7th Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement no. RI-283493

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. *Improving MPI communication latency of Euroben kernels.* **Chandan Basu.** http://www.prace-ri.eu/IMG/pdf/improving_mpi_communication_latency_on_euroben_kernels.pdf.
2. Home page of the EuroBen Benchmark. <http://www.hpcresearch.nl/euroben/index.php>.
3. *Towards runtime-clustering and improved implementations of collective operations in MPI.* **Chandan Basu, Johan Raber and Michael Schliephake.** March, 2013.
4. *A clustering technique for summarizing multivariate data.* **Hall, Geoffrey H. Ball and David J.** Behavioral Science, 12(2):153–155, 1967.
5. *Generic topology mapping strategies for large-scale parallel architectures.* **Torsten Hoefler, Marc Snir.** In Proceedings of the international conference on Supercomputing, ICS '11, pages 75–84, New York, NY, USA.
6. *Multi-core and network aware mpi topology functions.* **Mohammad Javad Rashti, Jonathan Green, Pavan Balaji, Ahmad Afsahi, and William Gropp.** Proceedings of the 18th European MPI Users' Group conference on Recent advances in the message passing interface, EuroMPI'11, pages 50–60, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011. Springer-Verlag.
7. *Design and evaluation of network topology-/speed- aware broadcast algorithms for infiniband clusters.* **H. Subramoni, K. Kandalla, J. Vienne, S. Sur, B. Barth, K. Tomko, R. Mclay, K. Schulz, and D.K. Panda.** 2012 IEEE International Conference on Cluster Computing, 0:317–325, 2011.
8. *Design of a scalable infiniband topology service to enable network-topology-aware placement of processes.* **H. Subramoni, S. Potluri, K. Kandalla, B. Barth, J. Vienne, J. Keasler, K. Tomko, K. Schulz, A. Moody, and D. K. Panda.** SC Conference, 0:1–12, 2012.
9. *The neighbor-joining method: A new method for reconstructing phylogentic trees.* **N. Saitou, M. Nei.** Molecular Biology and Evolution, 4(4):406 – 425, 1987.
10. *A review of hierarchical classification.* **Gordon, A. D.** Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series A (General), 150(2):pp. 119–137, 1987.
11. *Classification and Regression Trees.* **Leo Breiman, J. H. Friedman, R. A. Olshen, and C. J. Stone.** Statistics/Probability Series. Wadsworth Publishing Company, Belmont, California, U.S.A., 1984.
12. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing.* *R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria, 2013.* R Core Team .